

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Olivier****FIRST NAME: Habimana****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert some references

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 2016

ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The doctorate degree is the highest academic achievement one can get and although it has many rewards including high intellect recognition it goes with high expectations from different collaborators, in both academic and non-academic career pathways, about the quality of the work the role holder undertakes. A key distinguishing characteristic of a doctorate degree from other lower level of educations such as Master of Business Administrations, Master of Philosophy and Masters of science, is the writing and publishing high quality research papers and an academically rigorous dissertation, a document with a volume ranging from 100 to 200 pages in average required by graduate programs that I visited before choosing EUCLID. This condition makes publishing research papers being considered as the rites of passage to enter in researchers' community with a doctoral thesis playing a role of a passport in the academia (Blicblau, McManus and Prince 2009, 199), the segment of the population recognized for high intellect.

Since like other graduate programs, EUCLID has an objective of building the ability of doctorate candidate to "write professional, journal-grade academic papers," it goes to show that writing is an essential soft skill which is transferred to doctoral candidate to enable them to successfully write, with publishable quality, on their area of specialization. It is not surprising therefore that the ACA-401D was the first course to undertake with its period one being dedicated to the fundamentals of academic writing with topics ranging from essay writing to Chicago Manual Style through grammar, which is a toolkit for a doctorate student who is trying to learn the written rules of the publishing game with a little experience of facing the academic audience comprised of readers, reviewers and examiners. Throughout the following sections, I will discuss key concepts such as writing process, paragraph organization, correct grammar, ethics, and writing style that I found

enlightening to my both academic and technical writing competences that require certain standards of the written work both structurally and linguistically.

2) THE WRITING PROCESS

Despite my fourteen years' experience in development organizations requiring extensive writing of reports of all sorts such as donor focused narrative report and proposal documents, the content of the period one made sense of insisting guidelines from my employer organizations and feedback reviews from donors; writing is a process that needs to be diligently approached. The academic essay writing is similar to the technical writing I am used to in the sense that its objective is to ensure the type of audience such as reviewers and examiners are persuaded of the relevance of the content, concept, idea or finding to the 'research' question or task by the quality of evidence and examples used while the difference is in the depth of the evidence and credibility of their sources since they have to come from academic and/or peer reviewed academic texts (EUCLID 2019, 1). The ACA401D course pack for period one provides a comprehensive step by step guide of the process flow of the essay writing process that I have summarized into structuring of ideas, writing a rough draft, revising and editing.

The Benjamin Franklin's quote "Either write something worth reading or do something worth writing" is a proper reflection of the needs to plan the content of the essay or research paper well and longtime enough to be able to write them in a way that readers will easily capture the message and follow the idea flow in case of a longer piece of work. This connects well with my goal of writing simple, clear and elegant document which cannot be achieved without proper reflecting on the topic or question, dressing up a plan, searching what is known (reading) and unknown (research) to the topic, organizing thoughts and evidence with a document layout before starting to put them together before revising and editing (EUCLID 2019, 1 - 3). Although I follow the client's or donor's report structure the way ideas are organized into paragraphs is not well though before as I just put down sentences to explain data losing an opportunity to give my write up a good structure that is worth reading, and worse enough the intention has always been to persuade the donor that the project is going well as planned no matter what challenges and failures it faced, yet I could add the opposing views to balance the arguments (EUCLID 2019, 4). With the guideline that the writing process of revision and edition are also necessary for the writer reminded me that because of no proper planning I end up getting my so-called final document few minutes before the deadline and I most of the time skip the revision and edition stage or leave it for other colleagues and in very few occasion I check what the change they made; this is why most of the comments from reviewers are more related to the typos and missing words or incomplete sentences and sometime contradicting arguments. This course has provided me with space to introspect my writing process and I realized that I can write beautiful and engaging documents should my writing process get more organized and though through.

3) PARAGRAPH ORGANISATION

Exploring the content of the ACA401D course pack, although not specifically mentioned in the text, I realized that essays or other form of academic writing are not a mere mixture of sentences put together in an unordered flow. I remember back in secondary school and early undergraduate level that we were taught the structure of essays being an introduction, body and conclusion but I had not realized (or probably not taught) that the all paragraphs whether at introduction or conclusion level, are also further structured into topic sentence, supporting sentence and concluding sentence (EUCLID 2019, 3) in that order. In the pursuit of my writing's triple objective of simplicity, clarity and elegance I realized that while an effective paragraph should have sentences that are unified and coherent in a way that the reader would find it easy to follow different ideas conveyed by the sentences, there should be a coherence between different paragraphs within a text to contribute to the main argument (or thesis) of the text; this is the reason I have inculcated advices such as "state the main thesis," and "achieving logic flow," as well as "using linking words" (EUCLID 2019, 11 – 15) in my mind.

It is not surprising that throughout the ACA401D course pack linguistic guides and rhetoric aspects were mixed; together they form the building blocks of an effective paragraph. Having a main idea (argument) introduced by a topic sentence and explained by a supporting sentence with all sort of evidences without proper formatting and good grammar, will not achieve the 'elegance' objective and will make it hard for the reader to find the writing "worth reading" as per Benjamin Franklin advice. For example, while the length of sentences can lead the reader to lose focus, an improper use of punctuation can change the meaning of the sentence as evidenced by the in-text example on page 20 in the course materials where the inappropriate use of comma to separate items in a list after a conjunction increase ambiguity in a sentence (EUCLID 2019, 20). Another aspect of language that I found it needs more attention, especially for non-native English speakers, is the presence of run-on sentences and/or fragments in paragraphs due to omission of punctuation, verbs or subject which renders the paragraph turns to be incomplete.

Having both rhetoric and language focus in mind when writing is critical if one aims at delivering a paragraph worth reading. Going through reminders and guides in the course materials has enriched my "code of writers" and awaken my desire to revisit standard English grammar to perfect my knowledge of punctuation, type and structure of sentences, and linking words.

4) RULE OF STYLE IN WRITING

The reporting guidelines provided by donors, clients and/or multilateral organizations always shaped the way different type of documents narrative reports or project proposals should be structured and formatted. It is not very different from the academia or research community where different "style guides" are not only recommended but set as standard requirement. While EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (known as Chicago Manual of Style [CMS] or Turabian), other styles that are used by the

international scientific communities are accepted provided they are consistently used (Cleenewerck 2019, 24). Consistency is needed because these guides, in addition to universal correct grammar and vocabulary, set out a range of own rules for every writing element such as preferred length of sentences, layout, use of fonts, American or British spelling, preference for voice, use of heading and abbreviation, and citation that are not commonly well accepted, (EUCID 2019, 24 – 25) that can mislead the reader if used differently throughout the document. During my master's degree course, the university of London's preference was the style manual from the American Psychological Association (APA) with more focus on writing style and citing sources that use the Harvard referencing style. For example, in writing titles the Chicago lowercase prepositions (EUCLID 2019, 45) while APA capitalizes all words including prepositions (Alvi 2016, 54). The writing style, whether CMS or APA, provide writers with essential guide for effective writing that is accepted in the scholar community as they guide writers produce works that are clear, concise, uniformly organized and consistently delivered to the audience, rendering the reading easy to follow and checking for references (American Psychological Association 2019, xvii).

Going through the crib sheet in chapter eight of the course pack, I realized that Chicago Manual of Style has a comprehensive coverage of many elements of writing beyond style and usage of citations such page formatting, end/foot notes and mechanics of editing (EUCLID 2019, 44), justifying probably the reason behind EUCLID's preference. A combination of CMS and the Turabian manual provides a set of guidelines for the entire research process from selecting research topics to publishing research papers and graduate works such as thesis and dissertations. I will therefore constantly refer to both as the Turabian complements the CMS. However, I found the CMS not very rich in terms of writing about data and presentation of quantitative findings through figures and tables. This is an area that I will need to check with the course tutor on how to mics CMS and APA styles, which is reach on quantitative data presentation, while staying consistent.

5) CORRECT GRAMMAR

The imperative for writing a document worth reading by international audience requires not only the right structure but also the content that is grammatically free from grammatical errors. The ACA401A course pack prepares doctoral student to prevent this quality issue through several sections but the chapters 4 and 6 attracted my attention the most. In my opinion, the chapter 4 could have been titled "Basic Grammar for Writers" because it provides, through the "*Eleven (11) important Reminders,*" a selected list of the use of what I call "building blocks of Grammar" namely verbs, pronouns, modifiers (adjectives and adverbs) pronouns, nouns and the way they are arranged (syntax) as well as the role of proper punctuation in that arrangement (EUCLID 2019, 17).

As I alluded at it in the paragraph organization section, the use of punctuation before or after conjunctions confer a different meaning to the sentence in a similar way the use of "that" and "which" confer a restrictive nature of the sentence and can confuse the reader (EUCLID 2019, 19-20). The course material covered many common mistakes that student or beginner writers make repeatedly, ruining the quality of their work. This is

particularly important for international students whose first language is not English and to worsen the situation, those like me who have studied French in secondary school, English in undergraduate (taught by Rwandans who themselves studied in the US) and British English in Master's level, and now EUCLID requires the use of American English despite the ambiguous mention that “. . . but both versions are obviously accepted.” (EUCLID 2019, 24) The comparison between standard American English and British English was a relief to me because although I knew the two versions exist I had no idea of the negative effect caused by mingling them in the same text. I also recognized that there could be different spelling of the same word, different pronunciation of the similarly spelled word and different meaning of the same word (EUCLID 2019, 27-28). I recognize this was a wakeup call for me, and an invitation to consult the *Merriam-Webster's collegiate Dictionary* was a good guide. Moreover, I could not find the mention of the use of question marks and exclamation points in the academic writing practice. While I assume that the exclamation marks could be more suitable for creative writing than to academic, I hesitate to take the same approach to question marks because at some point in undergraduate I was taught that a good way of creating a hook in the introduction of the essay is to ask a question.

6) ETHICAL WRITING

All graduate schools I explored before choosing EUCLID consider that one of the key quality considerations by both academic (examiners) and journal levels, in assessing the quality the dissertation, is the depth of contribution to the existing knowledge and originality and the originality of the proposed publication. The definition and example of plagiarism practices given by the ACA401D course pack reminded me of the writing practices of copy-pasting and paraphrasing of other authors ideas without acknowledging the source that I had adopted during my undergraduate studies constitute the act of plagiarism that is “a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.” (EUCLID 2019, 5) The exploration of the EUCLID submission guidelines and the course material emphasize the need to not only be ethical but also perform literature review or desk research in an ordered way to explore existing ideas, build my own point of view of them and develop my argument based on what could be missing or wrongly interpreted by the authors in the same field of enquiry. Showing the knowledge and critics made to the existing literature can be used to strengthen the two qualities of the academic research: originality and contribution and the opposite, failure to give credit to others, only slows down the pace to the ‘rite of passage’ to the researchers’ community.

There are many ways one can use to balance originality and contribution such as paraphrasing, using quotes and citations (EUCLID 2019, 6) and the course materials present a wide range of instruments and tactics in chapter 2, 3, 5 and 8 that the writer can use to give own voice to the work. EUCLID's preference of “Turabian” or Chicago rule has not only widened my knowledge of a new style but also understanding of the importance of knowing the style guide of the publisher, journal or schools since they use their preferred style. For example, in-text citing using Turabian is different from the Harvard one in terms of the placement of the reference, its content and punctuation: while

the former add the page of the passage in the citation, the latter only considers the author and the year of publication.

The ACA401D course is a perfect guide to avoid plagiarism as it gives plenty of rhetoric and linguistic touches beyond appropriate use of citations, footnotes and biographies. There is a mention of tools such as Grammarly, Questia and Zotero, that I will learn throughout the remaining part of the course that gives me hope that I will emerge a plagiary-free writer.

7) CONCLUSION

Attending the ACA401D course has started on a good note, awakening my writer's spirit in me. Being extrovert and having an engineering background has shaped my love for writing to communicate my ideas, technical recommendations and develop strategies for organizations I worked for. The course has so far taught me the fundamentals of writing at a new level – the doctorate – and for an international audience that expects a high level standard of my research papers that follow internationally accepted writing style, with good organization of paragraph, and correct grammar that were put together complying to ethical standards. It is clear that the writing process needs to be understood and followed by the writer to achieve that standard. The course materials covered those aspects well and have helped me understanding the requirement from EUCLID and its difference with other graduate institutions I have attended, especially in the different examination forms I will have to prepare and submit. The period one of the ACA401D has aroused intense desire to perfect my writing skills and with no doubt, I believe that the remaining blocks in the ACA401D and the critical thinking course that will follow will leave me a great writer who will successfully communicate impactful insights to both research community and sustainable development practitioners.

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